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CREATIVITY IN COMPUTING EDUCATION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Creativity is an important skill for the 21st century, including for the computing industry, but it is not well understood how creativity is taught and evaluated in computing tertiary education. This study presents the results of a work-in-progress systematic review of creativity studies in computing published between the years 1990 and 2021, from two databases: IEEE and ACM. The databases were searched for publications defining creativity or discussing theories of creativity in Computer Science (CS), and/or conducting creativity training exercises and creativity experiments with undergraduate or postgraduate students or both. Focusing on instruments used in measuring creativity, how creativity has been measured and in which ways creativity is taught, our systematic literature review identified 26 key publications. Common methods for teaching and evaluating creativity are highlighted as relevant for educators identifying how they can build students' creativity skills. Limitations are discussed.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Creativity is one important generic skill that most employers prefer in their employees. Creativity being the origin of innovation is what employers are looking for, as they need innovation to stay competitive. Similarly, computer science is an important part of computing research and innovation, hence it is important that CS graduates are creative and employable in the industry for finding creative solutions to computer problems. Universities, therefore, must focus on ways to enhance students' creativity skills to meet the needs of employers in the ICT industry. Finding ways to teach creativity would be an ideal way of preparing computing students for industry. However, in the context of changing learning technologies, the process could be complex and time consuming. The definition of creativity, its importance, and ways of implementing creative learning techniques also vary for different professionals. However, the primary idea of being creative is to let the students explore their ideas and implement the ideas into reality. There is a need to find ways of implementing creative skills and behaviours in future professionals.

1.1 Background

In a 2020 report published by the World Economic Forum on the future of jobs, creativity was rated as the 5th top skill required globally as we move towards 2025 [1]. Specific to the field of ICT, academic studies have shown that creativity is an important skill for employees to possess. A study conducted on the perceptions of ICT students, lecturers and employers demonstrated that each group believed being creative and innovative was an important skill needed by ICT graduates [2]. A similar study conducted in Sri Lanka with university graduates, lecturers and employers from the field of ICT also found that each group perceived that individual creativity was a necessary skill to stand out in this competitive industry [3]. These outcomes demonstrate that creativity is a skill which is needed globally as we move into the 21st century, and that creativity is a key skill which is sought by employers in the ICT industry.

1.2 Motivation

There are various theories of creativity in the academic field and different explanations of creativity measures. Since creativity is becoming an important skill for future employability of computing students, we investigate the methods in which creativity has been previously taught in the Computer Science (CS) curriculum.

1.3 Contribution to the Literature

There is a lack of understanding about the diverse ways that creativity is taught in computing education globally. This study presents the results of a work-in-progress systematic literature review which explores creativity in computer education, including how creativity has been (i) defined, (ii) measured, and (iii) taught. Literature reviews about creativity in other fields such as psychopathology research have provided important

insights about the field [24], and it is imperative that this level of understanding is also gained for the field of ICT.

In this study, the following research question was addressed:

- What metrics, methods or tools have educators used with the intention of increasing the creativity skills of computing students?

2 METHODOLOGY

This study implemented the systematic review method set out by Kitchenham [4]. The review is systematic because of the methods used in the survey of literature, inclusion and exclusion criteria set for the selection of papers, and the final selected papers that are clear and reproducible [5]. Working in a systematic way provides researchers with a process for writing literature reviews of the papers selected in a reproducible manner.

2.1 Search Strategy and Eligibility Criteria

The search was carried using the databases of IEEE and ACM, because these contain the key papers of computer science researchers and academics. The ACM also contains the curriculum documents for all CS degrees and courses. Initially, the search was also made within the Computer Science Education journal of Taylor & Francis online, however no relevant papers were found in the database from 1990-2021, and hence it was excluded. A scoping search was first conducted, to identify appropriate keywords and fields to be used in the primary search strings.

The Inclusion Criteria used for the search were:

- The study must focus on the study of creativity in the computer science field.
- The study must include an experiment/intervention conducted with undergraduate or postgraduate students.
- Publications must be from conference papers, journals, and book and in English.
- The search was restricted to publications between Jan 1, 1990 - April 12, 2021.

The Exclusion Criteria for the search were:

- The paper must contain full article.
- If the search resulted in article duplication (2 or more same article in the list), one of them is excluded.
- If the search resulted in a Proceeding's title only, it was excluded.
- The paper must not be a section of the session, book, article, magazine information or workshop information only.

For the IEEE database, the following search string was used:

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((("Document Title":creativ*) AND ( ("Document Title":"C.S.") OR ("Document Title":"computer science"))) OR (("Document Title":"C.S.") OR ("Abstract":"C.S.") OR ("Abstract":"computer science") OR ("Abstract":"C.S.")))
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For the ACM database, the following search string was used:

Title:(creativ*) AND (Title:(C.S.) OR Title:("computer science") OR Title:(" C.S. ") OR Abstract:(C.S.) OR Abstract:("computer science") OR Abstract:(" C.S. "))

The IEEE database search resulted in 42 publications which were either from conferences, journals, or books, while the ACM database research identified 141 publications. The paper screening was first done for article duplication, papers with abstract only or proceedings title only and book chapter or articles that were not available for download. 42 papers were excluded. The second screening was based on paper title, if it mentions creativity or not. 34 papers were excluded. The third and fourth screenings were done upon abstract and full article reading. The purpose was to look for interventions/experiments done for creativity in the paper. 26 papers were excluded from abstract reading, while 55 papers were excluded after full paper reading. All the above screening resulted in 26 papers for the final review, 10 from IEEE and 16 from ACM.

Figure 1: Review selection process.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Where Studies Took Place

A total of 26 studies were included in the final review (ACM-16, IEEE-10). Based on the country, the studies were conducted in Australia (n=1), Finland (n=3), New Zealand (n=1), US (n=15), Uzbekistan (n=1), Brazil (n=1), Poland (n=1), Sri Lanka (n=1), Germany (n=1) Taiwan (n=1). **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** shows the final list of papers including the country where the research has been carried out.

3.2 Methods or Tools used by CS Educators for Increasing Creativity of Students

The common ways that have been used by educators in teaching creativity, and their reference numbers are:

- Course Lectures [26][13][25][32], Computational Creativity Exercises (CCEs) [27][24][22][21][23]; Case Studies [12][20]; Game Design Activities [20][14]; Robots [9][19][8]; and Brainstorming [14][8].

In order to teach creativity, several educators have implemented course lectures, activities, or workshops over a period of time that would help in enhancing creativity [26][13][6][15][16][22][23]. These courses are coordinated and synchronized with teaching assistants and students to realize the maximum benefit from a creative environment. Some studies also focused on creating an interdisciplinary professional learning environment in the classes where the students and educators can cooperate and encourage each other to be creative[6]. Amoussou et al. suggested that these instructors

Table 1: Summary of the CS Creativity Papers Reviewed

Ref.	Country	Document Title
[6]	USA	Assessing creativity practices in design
[7]	USA	Ways to learn and teach creativity and design in computing science
[8]	Finland	Creativity-Supporting Learning Environment-CSLE
[9]	Finland	Creativity and intrinsic motivation in computer science education-experimenting with robots
[10]	USA	Promoting creativity in the computer science design studio
[11]	Taiwan	The Influence of Interactive Art of Visual Music on the Creativity of Science and Engineering Students
[12]	Brazil	The importance of productive dialog in computer science students' creative thinking
[13]	USA	A pilot study on the impact of creative achievement on academic achievement in media oriented CS1
[14]	Germany	Creativity room 5555-evoking creativity in game design amongst CS students
[15]	Poland	Nature of Creativity in Computer Science Education. Designing Innovative Workshops
[16]	Finland	CLAP-teaching data structures in a creative way
[17]	USA	Integrating computational and creative thinking to improve learning and performance in CS1
[18]	USA	Improving learning of computational thinking using creative thinking exercises in CS-1 computer science courses
[19]	USA	Sparking creativity in computer science for interdisciplinary students
[20]	Australia	Creative geeks? facilitating the creative growth of computer science students using engaging environments
[21]	USA	Building Computational Creativity in an Online Course for Non-Majors
[22]	USA	Helping Engineering Students Learn in Introductory Computer Science (CS1) Using Computational Creativity Exercises (CCEs)
[23]	USA	Examining the Impact of Computational Creativity Exercises on College Computer Science Students' Learning, Achievement, Self-Efficacy and Creativity
[24]	USA	Computational Creativity Exercises: An Avenue for Promoting Learning in Computer Science
[25]	Uzbekistan	Development of Creativity of Learners in the Course" Innovative Educational Technology"
[26]	USA	Teaching creativity in computer science
[27]	USA	Learning through computational creativity
[28]	USA	Supporting Creativity and User Interaction in CS 1 Homework Assignments
[29]	USA	Teaching to foster critical and creative TH!NKing at North Carolina State University
[30]	Sri Lanka	Promoting creativity, innovation, and engineering excellence
[31]	New Zealand	Paperclips, Circles, and Six-Legged Spiders-An exploration of self-perceived and measured creativity among CS students

are succeeding in many factors that promote creativity [6]. Offering a studio-based teaching style or creativity room for game design activities can also provide students with a creative environment facilitating increasing creativity [14][20].

The use of robots in courses or game design is also one of the common interventions that CS educators are implementing in their course work to increase motivation and creativity levels of CS students. Apiola et al [9] arranged a workshop based on creativity-enhancing working methods where students participated in designing future robots for CS1 and CS2 courses. Based on this open teaching experiment, more ideas on how to integrate robots in the curricula supporting creativity and motivation were developed [9].

Murimi Renita [19] at the Oklahoma Baptist University studied the effects of programming and robotics in fostering creativity in CS. Since robotics is an important tool for CS students and their interest in work, students in this study designed a creative product using robots during their student project course. It used a learning by discovery mechanism and students programmed the robot around a pursuit-evasion game termed 'Zombie tag'. This sparked creativity in students to design a product to include a robotics project and laboratory in their course offerings was demonstrated to the educators [19]. Introducing project work in a course curriculum is a method widely used by educators for

implementing creativity learning in their courses [33]. Gestwicki et al [7] suggested the conventional teaching method is limited to having students working only as per teacher's guidance thus inhibiting students' creativity and growth. Therefore, a change in the conventional teaching method is crucial. It is imperative to implement real world scenarios in classroom projects and activities and help students to work through a creative process and make them ready to tackle real world problems [34].

Brainstorming is a highly used method of educators to improve creativity in students cognitive processes by generating and evaluating ideas and innovations [8]. Brainstorming in CS courses is an important aspect of the creative game creation process where students are asked some questions promptly about creative environments or alternative solutions that they can purpose which evokes creativity in the students [14].

3.3 Ways that Creativity is Evaluated in Computing Education

Common metrics or tools used to measure creativity are:

- Survey [26][6][18][24][22][21][19][35] and Feedback [8][30]; Creative Achievement Questionnaire (CAQ) [13]; and Self-assessment [29][31]

Along with the courses that are designed to increase creativity in students, survey is one common metrics. Peteranetz et al [11] asked students to complete a web survey at the start of the semester long course and another survey at the end of the semester. The pre-course survey was about motivation scales and the post-course survey was about motivation and strategic engagement scales, the creative competency scales, the knowledge test, and the exercise evaluation. The common technique used is to include open ended survey questions such as 'How has CCE influenced your understanding?' and 'What suggestions do you have for improving the CCEs?' [22]. It is used to determine the basic concepts of methods and technologies that develop creativity [25].

It is also important to get feedback from the target audience on how they feel about the creativity exercise or course. Sometimes the feedback refers to the constructive feedback provided to the students helping them to keep on track. Other times feedback refers to the student feedback regarding the evolution of the project course. Alternatively, feedback is given by IT people to help students in their creative solutions for the IT industry [30]. One significant aspect of feedback is to understand the likes and dislikes of students about the creative method or tool, so that it can be modified or enhanced to be more important in the success of the course designed to improve their creativity [30].

A pilot study by Gestwicki et al [7] measured students' creative achievement using CAQs. The students' creative achievement here refers to the creative product made by the individual. CAQ comprise of 96 items divided into 3 parts: Self-assessment of their talent (13 areas) by the individual, concrete achievements in 10 domains of artistic and scientific endeavor (judged by experts) and free-response statements (3 questions) from

individuals about how they think others perceives their creativity. The purpose of the study is to include creative activities in the courses for improving students' motivation [13].

Whalley et al [31] gave students a self-reporting questionnaire (SRQ) where they were asked to rate their creativity in 56 domains of creativity. The students were asked to make judgements on their own creativity in relation to other people having similar backgrounds to them. The purpose of this evaluation was to analyze how domain-specific the students' ratings of their creativity skills may be.

3.4 Instruments of Creativity Measure

It was found that while most papers focused on intervention or experimental methods used for increasing creativity of students and the metrics used to measure creativity, only a few papers have mentioned the instruments used in measuring creativity.

Common instruments that have been used for measuring creativity are:

- TTCT (Torrance Test of Creativity Thinking) [26][30]; Creativity Domain Questionnaire (CDQ) [31]; Abbreviated Torrance Test for Adults (ATTA) [11]; Critical Thinking Assessment Test (CAT) [29].

The Torrance Test of Creativity Thinking is one of the most popular ways of assessing creativity [26]. The test includes a divergent thinking test where participants are asked for several responses to a single prompt [26]. For instance, in an experiment by Whalley et al [31], the students were asked for the alternative and creative uses they can find for products such as paperclips and bowls. The researchers then analysed how creative the answers were. The Torrance test is designed to trigger this kind of divergent responses to some products, ideas, figural or vocal prompts [31]. The responses are analysed based on how creative and novel the ideas generated are.

Chang et al [31] used ATTA as a research measurement tool for pre-test and post-test research design in their research. ATTA is based on the principle of TTCT but requires less test time and is meant for adults (at least 18 years old). The students fill in the Study Preference Questionnaire as a pre-test study of ATTA, then experience visual music interactive artwork and later complete a post-test study of ATTA. In three phases, the experiment analysed current creativity performance of students, explored creativity with students of different backgrounds in the second phase and finally analysed the effect of virtual music interactive artwork in creativity of students [11].

Another instrument used to measure self-reported creativity is the CDQ. Participants provide ratings of their creativity across 56 domains of creativity. The rating of each domain is given by a seven-point Likert scale. How creative do you think you are in a specific domain as compared to other individuals with the same domain expertise? is what one CDQ asks to be answered by the participants. CDQ-R (CDQ-Revised) is a follow-on mechanism having the SRQ (Self Report Questionnaire) of 21 questions scaled on a six-point Likert scale [31]. The other instrument CAT was validated by researchers

of Tennessee Tech University and the students in the experiment conducted by Vila-Parrish et al [29] took a pre and post course CAT test.

4 SUMMARY

In this systematic review, 26 papers were reviewed where all have followed one or more research methods to measure creativity. Most of the papers suggested various teaching methods that can be used by the educators to implement creative learning and enhance creativity skills in computing students. Having creative thinking ability will make students ready for professional jobs and will be beneficial for students, tutors, and the computing industry generally. From the studies to increase creativity skills in students, teaching faculties should be able to include a creative process in their course in any form of workshop, design, or projects. It might require more time for tutors initially, but the time and effort investment would be worthwhile to deliver a course successful in increasing creativity skills in computing education students.

4.1 Limitations and Future Work

This work-in-progress study is limited to 2 databases: IEEE and ACM. In future, this will incorporate 'Computing', 'Software Engineering' and 'Information Technology' also in our search criteria. This will increase the number of publications reviewed. Initial searches have identified this will include at least 145 publications from IEEE (up from 42 in this study) and 810 papers from ACM database (up from 141 in this study). This will provide a comprehensive understanding of creativity in the field of ICT education.

5 CONCLUSION

Even though creativity is a subjective topic and is difficult to measure, it is obvious from the papers reviewed that it is an important soft skill required in the professional world. To prepare students for the future, educators need to find ways to curate their courses from the traditional teaching methods to ones that can spark creativity in their students. With the increasing use of robotics and automation in today's daily life, it is essential that students are prepared to take real world and robotics challenges that may appear throughout their careers. Also, with the uptake of new modes of work, increasing numbers of students will need creativity skills to become successful entrepreneurs.

This systematic review paper provides several suggestions to educators on the methods that are being used to teach creativity, how creativity can be evaluated or measured, and which instruments could be useful in what context of measurement. The aim is to encourage more CS educators to plan for their course and implement innovative methods to teach creativity to their students. Creativity is becoming more and more important and hence it is essential for CS educators to teach and support the students in learning creativity as much as possible.

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